

Studies on Aryl Thiosemicarbazones and 2-Oxo- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones[†]

V. S. JOLLY* and K. P. SHARMA

Chemical Laboratories, Government Model Science College, Gwalior-474 011

Manuscript received 22 September 1989, accepted 6 December 1989

A number of aryl thiosemicarbazones and 4-oxo- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones have been synthesised and tested for *in vitro* activity against *M. tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v) and antiviral activity for AIDS.

THIOSEMICARBAZONES have been reported to possess various biological activities¹. 4-Oxo- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones have emerged as potent tuberculostats and leprostatic agents². Wide range of biological activities³ have been reported with products derived from cyanoethylated tertiaryamino-benzaldehydes and 3-methoxy-4-allyloxybenzaldehyde. Keeping these in view it was thought worthwhile to synthesise 4-aryl thiosemicarbazones (1) and 4-oxo- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones (4 and 5) and to screen them for tuberculostatic and antiviral activities.

4-Aryl thiosemicarbazides on reaction with bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehydes gave 4-aryl thiosemicarbazones (1) in high yields. The thiosemicarbazones (2 and 3) on reaction with chloroacetic acid or α -chlorophenylacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate yielded 4-oxo-5-(unsub-

stituted/substituted)- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazones (4 and 5). Structures of the compounds have been confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis and IR spectra.

The aldehydes⁴ and 4-aryl thiosemicarbazides⁵ were prepared by reported procedures.

Anti-HIV activity: The compounds were screened for antiviral activity for AIDS which involved susceptible human host cells. 4-*N,N*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene-4-oxo-5-phenyl- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazone (4; R=H, R'=C₆H₅) showed 55.80% control and the response of 2-methyl-4-*N,N*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene-4-oxo- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazone (4; R=CH₃, R'=H) was 35.80% on infected plates. The thiosemicarbazones (1) did not show anti-HIV activity.

Antitubercular activity: The representative compounds were incorporated into Lowenstein-Jensen egg medium having concentration of 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and were inoculated with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇R_v strain, incubated at 37° and observed weekly for the growth of organisms for eight weeks. Compound 1 (R=OCH₃-*p*) inhibited the growth of *M. tuberculosis* at 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Other compounds were found to be inactive at the concentration used.

Experimental

1-(4-*N,N*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone. **General procedure:** To a solution of 4-*N,N*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.001 mol, 0.23 g) in ethanol (10 ml), glacial acetic acid (5 drops) and a solution of 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (0.001 mol, 0.17 g) in ethanol (5 ml) were added. The contents were refluxed for 45 min on a steam-bath. The resulting solid was collected under suction and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid as pale yellow crystals (75%), m.p. 195° (Found: C, 64.01; H, 4.98; N, 22.29; S, 8.40. C₂₀H₂₀N₆S requires: C, 63.82; H, 5.31; N, 22.34; S, 8.52%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 600-1 620

† Presented at 25th Annual Convention of Chemists, 1988.

(C=N), 1 185–1 210 (C=S), 2 250 (C $\equiv$ N) and 3 000–3 100 cm⁻¹ (NH).

Other 4-aryl thiosemicarbazones were prepared similarly (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
4-Aryl thiosemicarbazones (1)				
H	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ S	195	75
H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ S	198	59
H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ S	185	77
H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ OS	210	62
H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ OS	174	70
OH	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ S	194	64
CH ₃	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ S	211	74
CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ S	196	61
CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ OS	209	62
CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ OS	199	69
OCH ₃	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ OS	194	61
OCH ₃	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ OS	220	71
OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ OS	191	64
OCH ₃	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₂ S	212	69
OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₂ S	175	64
Hydrazone (4)				
H	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₆ OS	254	58
OH	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₆ OS	258	42
OCH ₃	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S	266	65
H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ OS	250	51
CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₆ OS	245	49
OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	257	50
Hydrazone (5)				
	H	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S	209	70
	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S	216	52

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

4-*N,N*-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene-4-oxo- Δ^2 -thiazolin-2-ylhydrazone. *General procedure*: A mixture of 4-*N,N*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene thiosemicarbazone (0.30 g, 0.001 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.1 g, 0.0012 mol) and sodium acetate (0.1 g) was ground and intimately mixed. Ethanol (10 ml)

and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) were then added and the contents refluxed for 2 h. The solid which separated out on cooling was filtered under suction and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow crystals (58.8%), m.p. 254° (Found: C, 56.56; H, 4.32; N, 24.60; S, 9.30. C₁₆H₁₆N₆OS requires: C, 56.47; H, 4.70; N, 24.70; S, 9.41%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 600 (C=N), 1 680–1 720 (C=O), 2 250 (C $\equiv$ N) and 3 015–3 140 cm⁻¹ (NH).

Similarly thiosemicarbazones of other aldehydes were condensed with chloroacetic acid or α -chlorophenylacetic acid (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors feel indebted to Dr. S. R. Trivedi, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amargadh, for testing tuberculostatic activity and are grateful to the Director, National Cancer Institute, Maryland, U.S.A. for anti-HIV drug screening results and to Director, D.R.D.E., Gwalior for ir spectra.

References

1. R. BEHMISH and H. SCHMIDT, *Am. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1950, **1**, 61; PERRY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 3591; SAGHER and BRAND, *Int. J. Leprosy*, 1958, **21**, 161; LOWE, *Leprosy Rev.*, 1954, **25**, 186; D. HAMER, J. BERNSTEIN and R. DONOVICK, *Proc. Soc., Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1950, **73**, 275; V. K. PANDHY and A. K. AGRAWAL, *Acta Chem. Indica, Ser. Chem.*, 1980, **6**, 166; A. CHIARINI, J. GIOVANNIMETTE, P. SINIBALDI and A. M. PALENZONA, *Farmaco. Ed. Sci.*, 1981, **36**, 33.
2. N. P. BUU-HOI, N. D. XUONG and N. B. TIEN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 415; N. P. BUU-HOI, N. D. XUONG and F. BINON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 713.
3. V. S. JOLLY, private communication.
4. V. S. JOLLY and P. I. ITTYERAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 997; S. K. P. SINHA and D. N. CHAUDHARY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 34.
5. KAZAKOV and POSTOVSKII, *Izvest. Tekhnol.*, 1961, **4**, 288; V. S. MISHRA and R. S. VARMA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 628.